

Stimulator Trigger Accuracy

An overview of how stance phase duration was determined is described in the main text. Here, we provide further data about the accuracy of the stimulator trigger accuracy. Force plate data, along with stimulator trigger signals, from participants of the final data collection phase of the study were used to test the accuracy of the trigger mechanism post-hoc, and verify it was indeed stimulating the nerves at mid-stance. Figure A1 shows a histogram of stimulator trigger time as a percentage of stance phase time, based on post-hoc calculations of force plate data. All data falls within 40-60% of the stance phase. Based on the works of Capaday and Stein, we do not expect H-reflex responses to vary significantly over this range of the stance phase.¹

Figure A1. Stimulator accuracy based on post-hoc calculations performed on randomly sampled force plate and stimulator trigger data.

Ruling Out Reciprocal Inhibition

It is well-established that reciprocal inhibition is known to influence H-reflexes in the antagonist muscle, as evident from the works of Nielsens and others.² To investigate the effects of reciprocal inhibition on our results, we calculated the correlation between normalized H-wave amplitudes (see main text for more details), and the root-mean-square (RMS) EMG signals 200 ms prior to H-reflex measurements in both the agonist (GAS) and antagonist (TA) muscles. In the ipsi group, we found weak correlation with GAS ($r = 0.31 \pm 0.19$), but not correlation with TA ($r = -0.19 \pm 0.27$) background activities. In the contra group, we found no

¹ Capaday C, Stein RB. Amplitude modulation of the soleus H-reflex in the human during walking and standing. *J Neurosci*. 1986 May;6(5):1308-13. doi: 10.1523/JNEUROSCI.06-05-01308.1986. PMID: 3711981; PMCID: PMC6568550.

Capaday C, Stein RB. Difference in the amplitude of the human soleus H reflex during walking and running. *J Physiol*. 1987 Nov;392:513-22. doi: 10.1113/jphysiol.1987.sp016794. PMID: 3446790; PMCID: PMC1192318.

² Crone, C, Hultborn, H, Jespersen, B, Nielsen, J, (1987), Reciprocal Ia inhibition between ankle flexors and extensors in man.. *The Journal of Physiology*, 389 doi: 10.1113/jphysiol.1987.sp016652.

Nielsen, J. B. (2016). Human spinal motor control. *Annual Review of Neuroscience*, 39, 81–101. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-neuro-070815-013913>

correlation with either GAS nor TA ($r = 0.06 \pm 0.31$ and $r = -0.06 \pm 0.26$, respectively). The figures below show the correlations between background EMG activities in GAS and TA and H-wave amplitudes for individual subjects in both the experimental and control groups.

